

Microwave-mediated synthesis of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams with aqueous trimethylborane

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A new microwave-induced method for the preparation of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams is explored via aqueous trimethylborane-mediated reaction of the corresponding xanthates.

Keywords: Unsubstituted β -lactam, trimethylborane, xanthate, radical.

Introduction

We have been engaged in the synthesis and biological evaluation of β -lactams for more than 25 years¹. These studies have culminated in diverse methods, new molecules and natural products. 3-Unsubstituted β -lactams are crucial molecules since they can be manipulated to numerous other compounds using the concept of carbanion chemistry². On this basis, preparation of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams by a new method is an important objective. Considering the Staudinger cycloaddition reaction of imines and acid chloride, one may feel synthesis of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams is not that complicated. Acetyl chloride on Staudinger cycloaddition reaction with imines in the presence of tertiary base would be the simple choice for the synthesis of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams. But, this reaction did not yield 3-unsubstituted β -lactams regardless of the substituents present in the other parts of the molecules. To overcome the limitations, our group has identified Reformatsky reaction between imines and bromo ester in the presence of indium metal³. This reaction proceeds well in many cases, but it seems that the reaction is highly sensitive with respect to indium metal and substrates. An appropriate activation of indium metal seems to be necessary for the success of this reaction. Unlike many other indium-in-

duced reactions, Reformatsky reaction was not possible in aqueous medium. Moreover, the indium-induced method works well with Schiff bases derived from monocyclic benzylic amines. In contrast, the success rate for the preparation of these types of compounds with sterically hindered imines is extremely low. It is understandable that the reaction with indium produces β -amino esters at the first step of the reaction. These intermediates fail to cyclize to β -lactams when less nucleophilic aromatic rings are present in the molecules. It is conceivable that 3-oxygen substituted β -lactams on deoxygenation can afford 3-unsubstituted β -lactams. In this paper, we describe microwave-assisted synthesis of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams through aqueous trimethylborane-mediated reaction of xanthates. Diverse β -lactams are prepared following this method.

Results and discussion

At the beginning of the work, synthesis of 3-xanthate-substituted β -lactams was undertaken.

Acetoxy-substituted monocyclic β -lactams **3-4** with different aromatic groups were prepared (Scheme 1, Table 1), the acetoxy group was then hydrolyzed with mild alkali to racemic 3-hydroxy β -lactams **5a-e** in excellent yields⁴ (Scheme 2, Table 2).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of racemic 3-acetoxy β -lactam via [2+2] Staudinger ketene-immine cycloaddition reaction.

Table 1

Entry	2		3 + 4	Time (h)	Yield (%)
	R ¹	R ²			
1	Ph	Ph	3a 4a	6	3a (80%) + 4a (0%)
2	Ph	PMP	3b 4b	7	3b (90%) + 4b (0%)
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	PMP	3c 4c	6	3c (85%) + 4c (0%)
4	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ph	3d 4d	5	3d (80%) + 4d (0%)
5	Ph	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	3e 4e	7	3e (85%) + 4e (0%)

Scheme 2

Table 2

Entry	2		5	Time (h)	Yield (%)
	R ¹	R ²			
1	Ph	Ph	5a	1	90
2	Ph	PMP	5b	1	90
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	PMP	5c	1.5	80
4	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ph	5d	1	85
5	Ph	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	5e	1	80

After the successful synthesis of hydroxyl β -lactams, the hydroxyl functionality was converted to xanthate esters **6a-e** in good to excellent yield by forming an alkoxide ion by reaction of sodium hydride with the corresponding unprotected hydroxyl group of β -lactams in dry THF. The resulting alkoxide ion on reaction with carbon disulphide afforded the sodium salt of xanthate ester which on alkylation *in situ* with methyl iodide produced the thio carbonyl-O- β -lactams **6a-e** in an excellent yield (Scheme 3, Table 3).

The replacement of xanthate group is one of the fundamental reactions that proceeds through radical formation in a two-step sequence⁵. The first step involves in the transformation of hydroxyl groups to O-thiocarbonyl compounds and the second step is azoiso-butyro nitrile (AIBN) and tributyltinhydride-mediated free radical chain reaction to replace the xanthate to hydrogen atom.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of β -lactam xanthates.

Table 3

Entry	R ¹	R ²	6	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	Ph	Ph	6a	5	90
2	Ph	PMP	6b	5	85
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	PMP	6c	6	80
4	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ph	6d	7	75
5	Ph	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	6e	7	70

This classical reaction has a disadvantage of using Harsh reaction condition and heavy metal.

Here in we wish to report mild and efficient protocol for deoxygenation of xanthates **6a-e** by hydrogen atom under automated microwave oven with aqueous trimethylborane in toluene⁶.

The reaction was rapid and the yield of the product of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams **7a-e** was excellent regardless of the nature of the aromatic groups at the -N or C-4 position of the β -lactam rings (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Synthesis of 3-unsubstituted β -lactam under microwave condition via trimethylborane-water complex mediated reaction.

Table 4

Entry	R ¹	R ²	7	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	Ph	Ph	7a	5	80
2	Ph	PMP	7b	8	75
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	PMP	7c	6	60
4	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ph	7d	5	65
5	Ph	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	7e	7	70

After the successful synthesis of 3-unsubstituted racemic β -lactam we expanded the scope of the methodology to optically active β -lactams. For the synthesis of optically ac-

five 3-hydroxy β -lactams, we used R-(+)-isopropylidene glyceraldehyde as a chiral auxiliary derived from 1,2:5,6-di-O-isopropylidene-D-mannitol⁷.

The R-(+)-isopropylidene glyceraldehyde derived Schiff bases with diverse aromatic aldehyde were employed for the synthesis enantiomerically pure β -lactams with acetoxy acetyl chloride (**1**) in triethylamine as a base in anhydrous dichloromethane and this method produced the 3-acetoxy β -lactams **9a-c** with excellent stereoselectivity and yield. The acetoxy group was then hydrolysed with 10% LiOH/H₂O system to yield the corresponding 3-hydroxy- β -lactams **10a-c** quantitatively (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Synthesis of optically active 3-hydroxy β -lactam by Staudinger ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

The 3-hydroxy group in **10** obtained from **9** was transformed into its corresponding xanthate **11** in the presence of sodium hydride in tetrahydro furan and carbon disulphide followed by the reaction with methyl iodide in excellent yield (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6. Synthesis of optically active β -lactam xanthates.

Entry	R ¹	11	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	Ph	11a	5	90
2	PMP	11b	5	80
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	11c	6	85

The xanthate was then removed with aqueous trimethylborane in an automated microwave oven as we described earlier (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7. Synthesis of β -lactam xanthates.

Entry	R ¹	12	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	Ph	12a	2	85
2	PMP	12b	4	80
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	12c	5	85

The mechanism of the process is complicated and novel. The reaction is initiated through a catalytic procedure by oxidation in the presence of air of the trialkylborane **13** to the methyl radical **14**.

The radical then reacts with the xanthate to produce S-methyl-S-methyl dithiocarbonate **16** and a radical intermediate **11a**. The (CH₃)₃B·H₂O complex **14** then provides a hydrogen for combining again with this radical to the 3-unsubstituted β -lactam **12** forming diethyl borinic acid and a new methyl radical. It seems microwave irradiation is capable of doing the series of catalytic pathways that are involved in this process⁶ (Scheme 8).

The method described herein is useful considering that xanthate appended with β -lactams is removed with aqueous trimethylborane in a microwave. These compounds are similar to the anticancer β -lactams reported earlier from our group⁸. In our future paper, we will describe the biological activities of our 3-unsubstituted β -lactams as well as further

Scheme 8. Plausible mechanism of deoxygenation of the xanthate group.

extend the scope of this method to optically active analogues. The notable part of this method is that this produces products in presence of oxygen and water.

Conclusion

An expeditious simple method for the preparation of 3-unsubstituted β -lactams through xanthates in a microwave oven is described. A wide range of substrates can be used for this purpose and therefore, this method can be used for the deoxygenation of relatively fragile molecules. Considering the biological activity of related analogues, this method will find applications to our cancer research.

Experimental

In a small microwave proof test tube, xanthate (1 mmol) was taken with toluene (1 mL), trimethylborane (2 mmol) and water (0.1 mL). The mixture was irradiated at 80°C for 5 min. The reaction mixture was diluted with dichloromethane (10 mL), washed with water (2 mL), organic part was dried with sodium sulfate and solvent was evaporated. The crude product showed identical IR and NMR data with the compounds prepared earlier by tributyltin hydride/indium-induced method⁸.

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